

USER-GENERATED-CONTENT MARKETING STRATEGIES IN PROVISION OF CONSUMER RESPONSIBILITY

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received March 15, 2024 Revised Apr 20, 2024 Accepted May 10, 2024</p> <p>Keywords: User-Generated Content (UGC), Consumer Engagement, Marketing Strategy, Brand Trust</p>	<p>This study examines the effectiveness of a user-generated content (UGC) marketing strategy in increasing consumer engagement. The research findings indicate that UGC marketing strategies can significantly enhance consumer engagement and strengthen the trust relationship between consumers and the brand. Audiences tend to trust consumer-generated content more than traditional marketing content due to its authenticity and genuineness. Therefore, marketers are advised to leverage UGC as one of the most effective marketing strategies to increase consumer involvement and achieve marketing objectives. By integrating UGC into their marketing strategies, brands can create closer relationships with their consumers and strengthen their market position.</p> <p style="text-align: right;">This is an open-access article under the CC-BY 4.0 license.</p>

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INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement of communication technology will result in alterations to the methods of communication used by people or groups. Marshall McLuhan said that technology has altered our methods of communication (Saefudin, 2008). The transition from analogue to digital technology has had a substantial influence on various domains, including marketing endeavours. As to Kotler and Keller (2008), marketing is a social process wherein individuals or groups fulfil their needs or desires by developing, offering, and exchanging free items and services that have value. With the advent of digital technology, the traditional marketing methods such as distributing brochures are being replaced by new approaches. The shift in marketing from being product-centric to customer-centric demonstrates how advancements in technology have expanded the availability of information, resulting in a diversified range of information sources. Furthermore, as the Internet increasingly assumes a pivotal role in fostering connections between companies and their customers, it gives rise to what is commonly referred to as

digital marketing. Marketers employ several strategies to introduce their products or services. The utilisation of both physical and online media is selected with the intention of capturing the interest of potential buyers. Marketers now choose online media due to its rapid and participatory nature. In addition, online media offers a cost-effective and highly targeted advertising platform, allowing advertisers to maximise the effectiveness of their funds. The advent of diverse social media sites, such as Facebook, Youtube, Instagram, and Twitter, each possesses its own distinctiveness. Users have the option to select the option that most aligns with their personality. Instagram appeals more to individuals that prioritise showcasing photographs or visuals as their primary means of communication. Youtube is appealing to those who enjoy watching or creating videos of extended length. Twitter is primarily used by individuals seeking active and interactive discussions. Facebook has the capability to handle both text and photo messages. TikTok is a social networking platform that is gaining popularity due to its unique features, which allow users to make and share short-lived films. User Generated Content, as defined by O'Hern (2013), refers to the unique content created by users in various forms, including physical things, voice recordings, computer programmes, and visual designs. This content is then shared extensively with other users and/or companies. Subsequently, this content is uploaded and disseminated to a broader audience of consumers, and can also be accessed by companies. Chia (2012) defines user-generated content (UGC) as the ability to produce various forms of media collaboratively and effortlessly, accessible to a wide audience, with low expenses, and open to feedback, purchasing, and endorsement. Consumers in today's fast-paced environment have a significant chance to directly impact marketing outcomes by sharing content that is based on their personal experience with the product (O'Hern, 2013). This aligns with the essence of Industry 4.0, which emphasises the rapid processing of user input in the form of online feedback. (Stevanov et al., 2017). User produced content is a characteristic of Web 2.0 that transforms the flow of communication from a unidirectional to a bidirectional format. Ankerson (2015) argues that the presence of user-generated content (UGC) highlights the importance of personalisation, involvement, cooperation, and sharing on the Internet.

The purpose of research on User-Generated Content (UGC) marketing strategies in increasing consumer engagement can include several aspects, among others: Identifying the effectiveness of UGC, i.e. Assessing to what extent user-generated content is more effective than content generated by companies in attracting attention and enhancing consumer involvement. Understanding the impact of UGC on Brand Engagement is to explore how UGC can influence consumer perceptions of brands, increase brand loyalty, and encourage more active interaction between consumers and brands. To identify the factors that drive consumers to generate UGCs is to investigate the motivation of consumers in producing and sharing brand-related content, as well as how companies can drive more UGC. To analyse the role of social media platforms in the distribution and impact of the UGC, and which platforms are the most effective for UGC-based marketing campaigns. Developing UGC-based Marketing Strategy is to formulate recommendations for effective marketing strategies using UGC to increase consumer engagement and company marketing goals. Evaluating the ROI of UGC Campaigns is calculating the return on investment (ROI) of marketing campaigns that focus on UGC compared to traditional marketing campaign. This research is expected to provide practical insights for companies to leverage UGC in their marketing strategies and create stronger relationships with consumers.

METHODS

Qualitative research is a broad and comprehensive research method aimed at understanding and explaining phenomena in their natural context. This qualitative study conducted interviews with 15 respondents who were active on social media. Data were analyzed using qualitative analysis using Miles and Huberman models. The qualitative method is a method of research that provides descriptive data results in the form of a narrative of events along with attitudes studied. We chose this method to gain a comprehensive understanding of social reality from the perspective of the study participants. This study also utilizes a representative sample population. There are entrepreneurs who use social media, especially businessmen who move into the fashion field, as their communication media, increasing their marketing in today's digital age. The technical determination of informants is done with purposive and snowball techniques. Data collection techniques include observation techniques, interviews, and documentation. Data analysis techniques used are data reduction, data presentation, conclusion drawing, and verification.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An innovative PR marketing strategy is implemented through the utilisation of User Generated Content, which involves leveraging social media content to influence the audience. User Generated Content (UGC) strategies on social media are often more trusted because the majority of the content aims to provide references about products used without any commercial motives[8]. Niantira argues that the interaction between brands and consumers in the MPR process might lead to effectiveness in brand awareness dissemination. This is indicated by positive testimonials from other consumers, which will also influence new target markets through user-generated content..

Naab and Sehl provide criteria for User Generated Content (UGC), one of which is that UGC is an individual's contribution. Internet users create their own content, easily accept or share content, and engage in other activities without qualification. The content consists of creative activities that are distributed through social media or other platforms, allowing other users to participate by commenting and engaging.

The research findings indicate that the content created by influencers and other content creators is their own original work, with each influencer and content creator having their own unique style in content creation. The followers of each influencer have a deep understanding of their content style and have a high level of trust in the quality of every recipe and other information shared by the influencer on their social media platform, in this case, Instagram.

Furthermore, it is imperative to publish User Generated Content. User Generated Content should be uploaded to a platform that is easily accessible by the public. Generally, User-generated content is disseminated through social media platforms. Distribution of information by email or instant messaging is not considered User

Generated Content. The User Generated Content activity being researched here pertains to the content on the social media platform Instagram.

Thirdly, User Generated Content is created outside of professional activities. TikTok leverages influencers with a substantial number of followers and high follower loyalty to enhance the credibility of its messages.

Influencers might originate from ordinary individuals as opposed to famous celebrities or artists, making them often perceived as more "authentic" and "organic". This statement is substantiated by the numerous interactions that occur between influencers and followers, where every attempt to recreate or emulate the recipes shared by influencer always yields successful results. Content created by influencers is typically more authentic and easily captures the attention of the audience.

Firstly, content detailedness refers to the quantitative information conveyed in the material. Abundant information and influencer experience in delivering products can reduce uncertainty about products and increase the likelihood that users find content useful.

The second dimension is content readability, which refers to how easily the influencer's product reviews in text form can be read and leave a positive impression on the readers, in addition to the voice content in videos. High readability indicates that the audience only need a relatively low level of effort and energy to comprehend the meaning of the text conveyed in the captions of Instagram reels and feed posts. Information objectivity refers to the degree of justice and impartiality. Excessive subjectivity in information can hinder the audience's understanding of the intended message, so disrupting their evaluation of the product and ultimately diminishing their trust in the content. The manner in which influencers express their opinions also has an impact on the opinions of their audience.

Displaying emotions is frequently regarded as undesirable as it could detract from the calibre of the topic, hence it is recommended to refrain from doing so when communicating information. The Instagram material of the influencer I follow consistently presents the same information, featuring captivating and informative photographs or videos that are primarily focused on preparing recipes. The words expressed are free of emotional content, presented with a happy demeanour, and successfully showcase the product's utility, so making it highly credible to the audience.

The fourth dimension that is as important is social acknowledgment. On social media platforms, especially Instagram, the "likes" feature is the most visible form of feedback. The audience's recognition of the quality of an influencer's uploads through "likes" serves as evidence that influencers have credibility in producing trustworthy content. The researcher's observations indicate that Instagram posts uploaded by influencers receive no less than 100 "Likes".

The fifth dimension is social popularity, which is reflected through the number of followers on social media. Interaction with the audience can also affect the audience's perception of influencers' beliefs. An account with a large number of followers is directly

proportional to the level of trust the audience has in what the influencer conveys, thereby promoting a more positive evaluation. Dwityas asserts that User Generated Content is more trusted than content sent directly by marketers or companies. Furthermore, Rusnali asserts that technological advancements through User Generated Content have the ability to reach and connect all segments of society without any spatial or temporal limitations.

The final dimension that is equally important is the interactivity of the creator, where influencers can provide more information to complement the ongoing activities. Through interactions in the comment section and direct messages, influencers can answer specific questions posed by the audience and establish a closer relationship with them. The interaction can generate more positive feedback due to the user's trust in the influencer. Interaction with the audience can also affect the audience's perception of influencers' beliefs.

The research findings indicate that UGC has a significant positive correlation with consumer engagement and brand trust. Active respondents utilising UGC perceive content generated by other users as very pertinent and aligned with their needs. They also believe that UGC might enhance their trust in a brand because content created by other users appears more authentic and trustworthy. To maximise the effectiveness of user-generated content (UGC), marketers must take the following steps: Encourage user participation: Develop campaigns, contests, and platforms that incentivize users to create and share content. Enhancing content effectiveness: Ensure that user-generated material is pertinent and congruent with marketing objectives. Assessing achievement : Regularly analyse the effectiveness of User Generated Content (UGC) to maximise outcomes..

CONCLUSION

UGC marketing strategy can increase consumer engagement and build trust in a brand. Therefore, marketers should use UGC as one of the effective marketing strategies in increasing consumer involvement and achieving marketing goals.

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